

GYMNASTICS LESSONS INCREASE THE PHYSICAL AND FUNCTIONAL CAPABILITIES OF YOUNG STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7949810>

ABSTRACT

This article describes the features of gymnastics lessons in educational institutions and its conduct, the important aspects of gymnastics in improving the physical and functional capabilities of students, strengthening their health, developing vital skills and cultivating special qualities.

Keywords: gymnastics, physical education, sports, physical and functional training, physical qualities, balance, posture, walking, running, jumping, strength, speed, agility, endurance and flexibility

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье описаны особенности занятий гимнастикой в общеобразовательных учреждениях и их проведения, важные аспекты занятий гимнастикой в совершенствовании физических и функциональных возможностей учащихся, укреплении их здоровья, развитии жизненно важных навыков и воспитании специальных качеств.

Ключевые слова: гимнастика, физическое воспитание, спорт, физическая и функциональная подготовка, физические качества, равновесие, осанка, ходьба, бег, прыжки, сила, скорость, ловкость, выносливость и гибкость.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada talim muassasalarida gimnastika darsi va uni o'tkazishning xususiyatlari, gimnastika darsi o'quvchi yoshlarning jismoniy va funksional imkoniyatlarini oshirishi, sog'lig'ini mustahkamlashi, hayotiy zarur malakalarini shakllantirishini va maxsus sifatlarni tarbiyalashidagi muhim jixatlari yoritildi.

Kalit so'zlar: gimnastika, jismoniy tarbiya, sport, jismoniy va funksional tayyorgarlik, jismoniy sifatlar, muvozanatni saqlash, qaddi-qomatni shakllantirish, yurish, yugurish, sakrash, kuch, tezkorlik, chaqqonlik, chidamkorlik va egiluvchanli.

INTRODUCTION

Physical education and sports are becoming an integral part of the daily life of young people as a guarantee factor in the formation of the nation's gene pool and the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of May 27, 1999 No. 271 "On measures to further develop physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan", the increase in the volume of physical education classes in educational institutions conceptual documents, such as the introduction of tests, and a special resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers on this issue, open up a wide range of legal and logistical opportunities for more rapid popularization of the industry, especially among young people. Gymnastics is included in the curricula of secondary

schools, academic lyceums and vocational schools as an independent subject. education, technical-tactical and game skills are of great importance in the development of spiritual-cultural, moral and psychological qualities.

The main purpose of physical education is to provide basic knowledge about "physical culture" and its components (physical education, sports, physical and functional training, physical qualities, etc.), the formation of life skills and abilities, the development of basic physical qualities. consists of.

Strengthening their health and physical fitness should be one of the most important issues for the teacher to make students aware of, not only as a personal matter, but also as a responsibility to society. Achieving this goal will allow to prepare the younger generation for a "big" life, to effectively organize future professional activities, to overcome the difficulties of life and to serve with honor in the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan.

DISCUSSION

The objectives of the physical education course are based on the above objectives: to strengthen health, develop general and special physical qualities, to teach the techniques of movement skills specific to a particular sport (gymnastics) and to form a sports discipline, respect for the opponent The course of physical education, including gymnastics, consists of 3 parts.

Part 1 - Preparation lasts 10-12 minutes and includes class organization (cleaning, informing the student on duty about the attendance, introducing the lesson tasks), line exercises, general and special exercises.

Exercises in the preparation of the lesson should be aimed at solving the objectives of the lesson. Preparatory exercises are designed to maintain the balance of the body, shape the body, walk, run, jump, strength, speed, agility, endurance and flexibility. The preparatory part of the lesson is to "warm up" the student's body and prepare it functionally for the main part of the lesson. The intensity of this part of the lesson should be gradually increased at first, and then slowed down again in the middle of this part.

The main part lasts 30-35 minutes. This section addresses the main goals and objectives of the lesson. Technical skills will be mastered. This is done by performing exercises related to the technical movement skills of the studied gymnastics. Teaching and shaping of technical elements can be done individually or in small groups and with the participation of all students. In this section, the teaching process is based on simple to complex principles, and the process of improvement must be very fast. The final part lasts 3-5 minutes. The purpose of this section is to relieve fatigue and restore the body's functions and ability to work with the help of exercises that relax and tighten the muscles performed at a very high intensity, as well as national movement games. During the course, the development of physical qualities, training and improvement of movement (technical-tactical) skills are carried out using various pedagogical methods. These methods include:

- explanation;
- show (demonstration);
- part-time training of certain skills;
- full and slow training at full speed;
- repetition;
- style of play;
- competition style, etc.

There are also incentives, punishments and persuasions in the teaching process.

Each method uses its own tools (exercises).

At the end of gymnastics classes, in most cases, there are active games. The purpose of such games is to calm the body and mind of the participants. The task of teaching and improving, including the exercises used, must follow didactic principles such as "simple to complex", "not passed" and "light to heavy" (in terms of load).

The quality and effectiveness of a lesson depends not only on the skills and experience of the teacher, but also on how well he or she prepares for a particular lesson. Preparation for the lesson includes the following activities:

- Designing (planning) the lesson process;
- Development of a model of effective and high-quality teaching;
- identify opportunities to ensure the useful intensity of the lesson;
- Appointment of student assistants;
- review the prepared and approved course report, make changes if necessary (course report is attached);
- consider the criteria for determining (assessing) the level of knowledge, skills and abilities of students;

RESULT

- review the location of the classroom, the readiness of the tools, equipment and supplies used;
- determine what the next lesson will be like after the lesson;
- The teacher pays attention to his appearance and sportswear;
- take into account the physical and functional capabilities of the students in the class.

In addition, the teacher must be armed with the following planning documents:

- educational standard and classifier;
- Annual distribution plan of study hours by curriculum sections;
- Annual schedule of classes, quarters and classes;
- Schedule of distribution of training materials by quarters;
- Quarterly work plan with lesson topics;
- class journal.

CONCLUSION

Conducting the lesson at a high level, ensuring the activity of students during the lesson, achieving a conscious approach to the implementation of tasks, instructions and exercises, instilling love and respect for the gymnastics lesson is a professional skill of the teacher and the effectiveness of the lesson. It is also directly related to his personal and human qualities.

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